

Research paper

Slicing vector fields into tool paths for additive manufacturing of nematic elastomers

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ABSTRACT

During additive manufacturing, it is normally assumed that the tool path does not affect the material properties, which is thus chosen to achieve the target geometry/strength while minimising the print time. However, in anisotropic materials the printing direction can be used to direct the anisotropy, for example, shear stresses during extrusion align liquid crystal elastomers (LCEs) along the print direction, which then dictates the direction of anisotropic deformations under thermal stimulation. By patterning the print direction, and hence the contraction direction, one can fabricate LCE sheets programmed to undergo complex deformations. Therefore, the slicing algorithm needs to provide control over both the geometry of the sample and the printing direction. In this work, we present a slicing algorithm which translates arbitrary planar unit vector fields into sets of print-paths, by seeding paths based on the divergence of the desired pattern. The manuscript is accompanied by an open-source implementation called *Vector Slicer*, and we demonstrate its capabilities by printing numerous LCE designs that reversibly morph from flat sheets into complex 3D shapes on heating. Previously, AM of LCEs has been limited to extremely elementary patterns sliced by hand. Our approach to slicing arbitrary patterns is thus a significant advancement for AM of LCEs and will enable similar patterned AM in a range of other materials.

1. Introduction

The original purpose of 3D printing is to rapidly fabricate bespoke geometries with minimal waste and short production lines [1]. However, as our suite of techniques and materials grows ever more sophisticated [2], a new possibility has emerged: printing with voxelized control over material properties. This technique can generate composite structures with sophisticated, almost organ-like spatial organisation. Thus far, most examples involve voxelated material composition, enabled by dynamically swapping inks for discrete multi-material structures [3–5], or dynamically mixing inks for continuously graded prints [6,7]. However, beyond composition, many material properties are also dramatically effected by microstructural features such as defect density, grain size, fibre alignment and gel fraction [8]. Traditionally, microstructure is manipulated via material processing steps like work-hardening, annealing or rolling, which are hard to voxelate. However, within a 3D printer, a degree of control can be achieved by dynamically changing print-process parameters, such as rate, temperature, tool-path or E/B field [9–14]. Such techniques can manufacture samples with uniform composition but bespoke graded microstructures that are inaccessible to traditional methods, and blur the boundary between material and structure [15]. However, in addition to

requiring the development of novel printing techniques, they also call for more sophisticated *slicers*, to translate graded designs into printer instructions.

Here, we focus on the printing of strongly anisotropic materials characterised by a single material axis of alignment (i.e. transversely isotropic), a class which includes muscles [16], wood, bone [17–19], laminates, composites containing aligned fibres [20], kevlar [21], and nematic liquid crystals [22]. When printing such materials, the ability to dictate the orientation of the material axis throughout the print allows optimisation of many corresponding mechanical and transport properties. For example, carpenters have long oriented the grain of wood along the direction of maximum load. Similarly, in biology, a complex pattern of muscle fibre alignment encodes the pumping of the heart [23], and the writhing of an elephants' trunk [24].

In many forms of 3D printing, it is natural for the material axis to follow the direction of the print path. This is particularly true during extrusion based printing techniques, where the shear forces can align polymers, fibres [9,10,12,25], liquid crystals [25–31] or other constituents of the ink along the extrusion direction; analogously, the crystal orientation of stainless steel follows the scan direction during

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Fig. 1. LCE actuation. A Actuation of a monodomain LCE sheet showing contraction on heating and B the corresponding experimental picture (2×1 cm at RT and 1×1.45 cm at 140°C). C Azimuthal alignment morphs under stimulation out of plane, forming a conical shell. In A and C the planar domain of the cold LCE sheet (S) is marked in gray and the director (\hat{n}) is shown as blue lines. (For interpretation of the references to colour in this figure legend, the reader is referred to the web version of this article.)

laser powder bed fusion [13]. Moreover, extrusion-based AM normally produces anisotropic objects even when using isotropic materials, as, for example, the strength is much higher in the print direction [32], motivating the orientation of print paths along the maximum stress (“stress line AM”, SLAM) [33].

This new manufacturing capacity has inspired several methods for designing patterns of anisotropy, including FEM stress analysis for SLAM-like prints [33–35], inverse solvers for morphing structures [10, 36] and topology optimisation for better mechanical and thermal properties [37–39]. Once designed, a pattern must be printed. Thus motivated, we report here on the development of a slicer that produces a desired planar geometry, by printing lines of constant width along a locally specified alignment direction, and ensuring uniform coverage with minimal gaps and overlaps between the print paths.

1.1. Motivation: AM of liquid crystal elastomers

Our development of such a slicer is motivated by a particularly exciting class of materials: liquid crystal elastomers (LCEs) [40]. In brief, LCEs are soft rubber-like polymer networks built from rod-shaped monomers (mesogens) that spontaneously align along a common director, described by the unit vector \hat{n} . On heating, the rods undergo a reversible transition from aligned to isotropic (reflecting the conventional nematic-isotropic phase transition, Fig. 1A), and this causes the LCE to contract by a large factor ($\sim 50\%$) along \hat{n} (Fig. 1A, B), much like a muscle contracts upon stimulation [41, 42].

There is currently considerable interest in fabricating LCE samples with bespoke patterns of alignment, as, on heating, these generate corresponding patterns of contraction, leading to complex programmed shape morphing [43, 44]. For example, a disk encoded with concentric director circles (azimuthal alignment) will morph into a conical shell upon stimulation [45] (Fig. 1C), and such LCEs are surprisingly powerful lifting machines, able to raise 2500x their own weight as they rise

Fig. 2. 3D printing of LCEs. A During the extrusion, liquid crystals, which are initially in polydomain nematic state, become aligned along the printing direction due to shear stress. B An image of complex director pattern being printed with a commercial KR2-15 print head from Hyrel [58].

into cones [46, 47]. In recent years, a wide variety of complex patterns have been designed, including analytic patterns for general surfaces of revolution [45, 48], sharp points [49, 50], sharp folds [51, 52], and iris, cylinder and evertor actuators [53]; concurrently numerical inverse solvers have also been developed to find the pattern for arbitrary surfaces such as faces [36, 54].

Two strategies have been developed for fabricating director patterned LCE sheets. The first (non AM) is based on surface alignment techniques, as familiar from LC displays [22]. In brief, the alignment direction is encoded onto a pair of glass slides, either by mechanical rubbing [55], or via photo patterning of a polarisation-sensitive command layer [43, 56]. The slides are then sandwiched together into a cross-linking cell, and a thin gap between them is flooded with an LC fluid, which adopts the desired pattern due to surface anchoring. The LC layer is then polymerised and cross-linked, to form a solid LCE sheet with the patterned director. This technique produces extremely high quality LCEs with arbitrary planar director pattern [43], but is limited to thin sheets, and specific chemistries. Furthermore, in practice, photo-command layers are difficult to work with, often producing inconsistent results [57].

The second approach is a form of AM: direct ink writing (DIW) [26, 28–30]. In this case, long LC oligomers are prepared as a viscous ink, which is then extruded through a narrow nozzle so that the extrusion shear forces orient the director along the print path, Fig. 2A. Concurrently, in-situ UV cross-linking turns the LC polymers into a solid LCE, locking in the orientation. Such 3D printing can be implemented straightforwardly using commercial high-pressure, high-temperature DIW print heads such as Hyrel’s KR2-15 [58], Fig. 2B, combined with a simple and popular LCE click chemistry formulation based on a two-stage thiol–acrylate Michael addition and photopolymerisation [59]. This simplicity and low cost of entry has driven widespread adoption. However, to date, 3D printed LCEs have been limited to extremely simple patterns: largely monodomains and azimuthal patterns. In contrast, complex patterns for faces, caps, irises etc. have always required photo-patterning. Fortunately, this does not reflect a fundamental limitation, but rather the lack of a slicer that can translate these patterns into print paths. Such path planning is difficult, as one must follow the convergence and divergence of the director lines whilst still maintaining a uniform fill density of printed lines so that the finished sheet does not have gaps. The requirement for a near-perfect fill is particularly stringent in LCE printing, as a print forming a web of paths connected only at nodes will inevitably just shrink uniformly on actuation, so complex morphing relies on adjacent paths bonding into a single continuous sheet. This situation contrasts with FDM of stiff plastics, where relatively low density “infill” is often preferred [60], even when patterning print direction for strength [33, 61].

1.2. Problem specification and previous approaches

In this manuscript, we thus tackle the following slicing problem. Given a region S of the x – y plane decorated with a desired alignment

direction described by the planar unit vector (director) $\hat{n}(x, y)$, design a print path for an AM tool that extrudes material lines of fixed width w (paths) to produce a sheet of material with the shape of S while everywhere extruding along $\hat{n}(x, y)$. Given we are motivated by LCEs, we focus on non-polar (tensor) materials where \hat{n} and $-\hat{n}$ describe the same physical state of alignment, so an extrusion line may actually be printed in either direction. However, we note that our approach can be trivially extended to polar materials, where the sign of \hat{n} must also be followed, although to-date no practical material printing system has this capacity, likely stemming from the tensorial character of stress.

This problem is quite distinct to traditional slicing problems, as it focuses on reproducing internal microstructure, rather than faithfully reproducing a 3D geometry. As a result, we obtain little guidance from the standard approach in which the boundary is directly followed then the interior is filled with a predefined infill. However, two analogous problems have been long studied in the field of computer graphics: the generation of stripe-patterns on surfaces with defined direction and spacing (e.g. zebra coats), and streamline plotting for visualising vector fields. Latterly, and both problems have inspired AM slicing techniques.

Stripe generation techniques solve for a continuous scalar field over the target surface, that oscillates such that, if its value is mapped to a colour or texture, a stripe graphic is formed. Early approaches produced such scalar fields in a bio-mimetic way, via the time-evolution of anisotropic reaction diffusion PDEs [62]. More recently, very efficient algorithms based on minimisation of an effective energy have emerged [63], which can typically generate stripe patterns in ~ 0.5 s, allowing an interactive user experience, even for stripes on non-planar surfaces. Both approaches have been used in AM for slicing along vector fields [34,35,64,65], with the paths taken along contours of the scalar field. The conversion of stripes to print paths requires a degree of post-processing, inevitably adding some computational overhead, and leading to a somewhat indirect relationship between the print paths and the stripe algorithm. Nevertheless, the approach certainly provides rapid and high-quality slicing results for the comparatively simple patterns of alignment generated by stress analysis, including on non-planar slices/layers [34,35,64], and with non-uniform target width [64].

Conversely, in streamline plotting, the integral curves of a vector field are typically directly propagated from “seed” points. Unlike with stripes, the resultant streamlines can be directly mapped to print paths. Streamline algorithms differ principally in their placing of seeds, their order of propagation, and their conditions for line termination/removal. Most streamline plotting approaches optimise these steps for qualitative visualisation of the field, with line density conveying field strength or chosen to capture topological field structures such as vortices, but there is also prior work on creating evenly spaced streamlines upon which slicing algorithms can be built [66–68].

Various such streamline approaches have also been adapted for AM. In [33] (SLAM), an initial seed is placed and propagated to make a first path, then a family of adjacent seeds with gradually increasing distance are propagated as candidate paths, with the next chosen path being the furthest seed that generates a streamline that no-where exceeds a user-defined maximum distance from the previous path. This results in a very open mesh structure with well-controlled maximum distance between paths, but no attempt to make a dense fill. Alternatively, paths can be propagated from seeds randomly placed over the domain [61]. After maximally propagating all seeds, one obtains a very uneven path density, which is then improved by removing paths that are too close to their neighbours, and seeding new paths between paths that are too distant. Similarly, in [69], seeds are placed on a regular square lattice over the domain, and then each propagated to their maximum extent to make a candidate path. Candidate paths are then selected as actual print paths in order of length, with a termination criteria applied to curtail paths when they approach an already selected path too closely; this idea is implemented efficiently using “double queue” algorithm originating in streamline plotting [67]. Both these

approaches achieve moderately uniform fill density, but fail to ensure adjacent paths actually abut along their length. For example, even with a uniform (or non-diverging) vector field, if two seeds are chosen with a spacing greater than a path width but less than two path widths, the resultant paths will never touch or terminate, but nor are they sufficiently diverged to seed a new path between them. This situation results in two long parallel print paths that are close but not joined; such long gaps between paths are clearly visible in the prints [61], but must be avoided in LCE printing.

Finally, a very recent work [70] explores a swarm-approach [71] to AM path generation, wherein a “swarm” of seeds are initiated at the boundary with a preferred spacing, then propagated concurrently through the domain with birth and death criteria based on their evolving spacing. This approach is very computationally efficient, but the resulting slices have a clear and undesirable directional bias based on the direction the “swarm” propagated through the geometry, and it remains unclear how to deal with loops in the field, which are particularly common in LCE designs.

For LCE printing, we need largely abutting/overlapping print paths that physically join together to make a single sheet. Furthermore, many desirable LCE director patterns are significantly more complicated than the stress-axis based patterns mostly sliced previously, often containing loops, defects, discontinuities and other rapid variations in director on a scale not much larger than the path width itself. We thus seek a robust approach, that can handle these difficult cases reliably. Our survey of recent AM work shows that both the stripe-generation approach and the stream-line approach are both promising approaches that could likely underpin a successful LCE slicer. However, ultimately, we decided to work in the stream-line approach. Firstly, two core advantages of the stripe-generation approach – slicing in 3D surfaces and computational efficiency – are less relevant for LCEs, where planar printing is ubiquitous, and the long timescales for synthesising (hours), printing (hours) and pattern design (days) make it very unlikely that slicing will ever be a bottleneck in the workflow. Secondly, stripe generation algorithms often produce features that are undesirable for AM of LCEs, including stripe branching/merging, deviations from ideal spacing, and (in rapidly varying fields) substantial mismatches between target and achieved director (e.g. Fig. 3E–F in [64]); branches/merges can naturally be trimmed from print-paths in post-processing, albeit at the cost of introducing gaps, but spacing and misalignment are intrinsic to the stripes and cannot easily be addressed post-hoc. Of course, stream-line approaches also produce similarly undesirable features: indeed, some degree of gaps/overlaps/misalignment is unavoidable, whatever approach is used. However, we are attracted by the direct relationship between print paths and stream-lines, which greatly facilitates the incorporation of printing priorities/constraints into the algorithm. Ultimately, this direct relationship enables us to explore trade-offs between these different types of defect, to robustly and reliably find acceptable tool paths for AM of LCEs.

Correspondingly, here, we report a splay-based approach for seeding print paths with highly uniform spacing. A key observation is that our slicing problem has no perfect solution, as regions with divergent director cannot be filled with lines of uniform width without some holes or overlap. However, by combining splay-based seeding with slightly relaxed path directionality constraint and a Bayesian optimiser to trade off gaps, overlaps and deviations from the perfect director, we are able to consistently obtain high-quality results (usual coverage $>95\%$, overlap $<10\%$, director deviation below 5°). We also validate our print paths experimentally, showing they produce appropriately morphing LCE sheets. An open source implementation of our approach is released as *Vector Slicer*, enabling LCE sheets to be printed with arbitrary complex director patterns and vastly increasing the capacity of extrusion-based LCE printing.

Fig. 3. Seed line based slicing and seed line spacing. A A streamline is propagated by selecting a seed within the pattern, and the line is obtained by directly following the field lines in both directions. B Base logic of a stream-line based slicing algorithm. C Logic for selecting seed lines, so that they can be consistently spaced. D Spacing logic for a single seed line.

2. Slicing procedure

Given a director field $\hat{n}(x, y)$ and a seed point (x_0, y_0) , one can directly propagate a line from the seed and along $\pm\hat{n}$ to form an appropriate candidate print path, Fig. 3A. Such paths are simply integral curves of the director field (also known as field lines for E/B fields, or streamlines for velocity fields) although printed with finite constant width. The essential problem is packing such lines together well, with even spacing, to generate a high quality physical print without gaps or overlaps, even in regions where the underlying vector field diverges or converges.

2.1. Seed line slicing

The key step to getting good results from this very simple approach is to carefully select a good set of seeds and an appropriate termination criteria. We thus start by considering how to select seeds for print paths. The simplest approach is to place seeds randomly, by, for example, drawing samples from a uniform distribution over S . However, as shown in Fig. 4A (ii), even in the simplest possible situation of a monodomain director (uniform \hat{n}), this results in a low quality pattern with non-uniform density, overlaps and gaps. A better approach is to first draw a single *seed line* perpendicular to the director and then space with constant separation w along this seed line to generate a perfectly packed design, Fig. 4A (iii). Seed lines are commonly used in visualisation, but, to our knowledge, are new in AM. A high level overview of a seed line slicing algorithm is given as a flow chart in Fig. 3B, which describes how one first identifies an initial set of seed lines, then takes the seed lines one by one, dividing them into seeds and propagating these seeds into paths, with the process continuing until no fillable areas remain.

This algorithm immediately anticipates that multiple seed lines may be used to obtain complete coverage in complex geometries. For example, a uniform director on an L shaped domain might be seeded with two seed lines, as seen in Fig. 4E. In this case, for even coverage, we must space seeds evenly along each line, but also consistently between the two lines, so that there is not a gap between their respective filling basins (Fig. 4E (ii)). A pragmatic way to achieve this is to artificially extend each seed line by w , so that their filling basins overlap. Having done this, when we consider the second seed line, we observe that it overlaps into the already filled area, and place the first seed $w/2$ away from the existing fill to ensure a perfect join.

Importantly, the seed line idea is also useful, even if the director is non-uniform. In this case, one can similarly construct seed lines that

run orthogonal to the director, although such lines now may be curved. Formally, these lines are known as dual lines as they are integral curves of director's orthogonal dual ($\hat{n}^* = R_{\pi/2}\hat{n}$), and such dual line seeding has been previously reported for streamline visualisation [72]. As shown in Fig. 4B, this approach can also produce perfectly packed designs for non-uniform directors, but only if the director pattern is splay-free ($\nabla \cdot \hat{n} = 0$), meaning the print paths do not diverge or converge, so paths launched with even spacing w remain at even spacing as they propagate. We note that, in splay-free fields, dual lines are in fact always straight, even if the director itself is curved [73].

Unfortunately, once patterns contain splay, dual line seeding encounters a problem: although the paths are seeded equidistantly they will converge or diverge away from the seed line generating overlaps and holes. For example, in Fig. 4C, we consider a radial director pattern, in which the dual lines are concentric circles. Seeding from such a circle at an intermediate radius, Fig. 4C (ii), gives paths that overlap within the circle, and diverge away from it. Whereas path convergence can be easily treated by appropriately terminating lines (next section), divergence is more problematic, as it leads to gaps which will only ever be filled by introducing more seeds. A simple approach is thus to identify where the paths have diverged the most, which for a radial pattern is the dual line around the perimeter. Seeding from this line indeed produces a pattern with overlaps but no gaps, Fig. 4C (iii).

However, in general, the perimeter of S will not coincide with a dual line, as seen in the case of a radial pattern on a square domain, Fig. 4D. In this square-radial case, using the perimeter still appears to be the best seeding approach, Fig. 4D (ii), as all paths are maximally diverged at the perimeter; in contrast, taking a dual circle within the domain will generate gaps between lines between the circle and the perimeter. However, when the seeding line is not a dual line, spacing seeds evenly along the seed line results in a variable path density, Fig. 4D (ii), as the seed line is not cutting the print paths orthogonally. Moreover, in such circumstances, where paths are diverging and converging, and perfect packing is thus not possible, it may be advantageous to space seeds with an effective width d_s , rather than the true path width w , so that spacing can converge/diverge towards w away from the seed line.

In general, if a straight line with tangent vector \hat{t} cuts through a print path of effective width d_s aligned along \hat{n} , the line stays within the path for a distance $d_s/|\hat{t} \cdot \hat{n}^*|$. Given seeds are at a path centre, for well-packed paths, we should thus place the i and $i + 1$ seeds with a separation l along the seed line given by

$$l = \frac{d_s}{2} \left(\frac{1}{|\hat{t} \cdot \hat{n}_i^*|} + \frac{1}{|\hat{t} \cdot \hat{n}_{i+1}^*|} \right) \quad (1)$$

Fig. 4. Different path seeding approaches. A Uniaxial director pattern with (ii) random path seeding and (iii) equidistant dual-line seeding. B When a pattern is filled using multiple seed lines, the spacing needs to be consistent both within the seed lines and between them. If the spacing is done disregarding other seed lines, avoidable gaps can form (ii). We avoid it by considering the seed lines in a sequence, where first the pattern is filled using a single seed line (iii) and then a neighbouring region starts spacing $w/2$ away from the previously filled area (iv), providing uniform coverage all throughout. C Azimuthal director pattern with (ii) equidistant dual-line seeding. D The dual line approach for the radial pattern with dual line started (ii) within the pattern and (iii) at the boundary. E Radial pattern on square domain with paths seeded on boundary using (ii) standard and (iii) field-structure-aware (Eq. (1)) distance functions. Left-most images represent the desired director patterns, with blue lines being the integral curves of the director. (For interpretation of the references to colour in this figure legend, the reader is referred to the web version of this article.)

where \hat{n}_i^* is dual director at the i th seed. Using this approach to seed the radial pattern from the boundary of a square domain (with $d_s = w$) indeed produces a good, even result, Fig. 4D (iii).

These considerations allow us to flesh out our algorithm for how to divide seed lines into seeds while ensuring consistent seed spacing both within and between seed lines. These details are provided as flow charts in Fig. 3C, D. However, the issue of how to best choose seed lines remains unresolved.

2.2. Splay seed line approach

The success of perimeter-based seeding for the radial pattern on a square domain stems from the fact that, in this case, the perimeter is the line of maximum path divergence. This suggests a general approach, which is to seed from the lines in the pattern along which the paths are maximally diverged, which may in general lie at the perimeter or within the pattern. To identify such lines, we use the splay vector $s = \hat{n}(\nabla \cdot \hat{n})$. Geometrically, s is a vector that points along the director, in the direction of path divergence and with magnitude given by the strength of the divergence; it also corresponds to the vector curvature of the dual lines [50,73]. Importantly, the direction of path divergence is unambiguous, independent of the sign of \hat{n} itself, so s is a true vector property of the pattern and invariant under $\hat{n} \rightarrow -\hat{n}$.

By traversing a director line in the direction of splay, we thus pass through ever more diverging paths, until we encounter the boundary of the pattern, or an area within the pattern where splay is zero. If the boundary is encountered, then this portion of the perimeter is a suitable seed line, as seen in the radial case in Fig. 5A. Furthermore, such segments of the perimeter can be readily identified as those with an outward pointing splay vector, which we label as boundary lines of peak divergence (B-PD) as shown in Fig. 5C. Conversely, boundary segments with inward splay vector are boundary lines of peak convergence

Fig. 5. Splay-based line propagation. A The splay in radial pattern points outwards from the centre, thus the boundary has B-PD character. B A pattern with boundaries of B-PC character and an internal line of I-PD type, which is the suitable seeding line. C Classification of candidate seed lines based on the sense of the splay vector. Boundary regions are suitable for seeding if the splay vector points towards the boundary (B-PD), while interior splay-free lines are suitable for seeding the splay on either side points towards the line (I-PD). D Pattern demonstrating both types of the boundary and all three types of zero-splay lines on the interior of the pattern, with lines suitable for splay seeding (PD) marked with bold caption.

(B-PC), and paths seeded here will diverge when propagated into the pattern, making such segments unsuitable for seeding.

In the interior of the pattern, we may identify further suitable seed lines by searching for the regions of zero splay ($s = 0$). In a generic splay-bearing pattern, these zeros naturally follow lines within the pattern dividing areas of opposite sign of the splay vector. However, as with the perimeter, not all such zeros are suitable seed lines, as they may correspond to maxima, minima or inflections in path density. Analogously to the perimeter seeding, these cases can be distinguished by looking at the signs of the splay vector, but, because such lines lie fully in the pattern, we must look at the splay vector on both sides, leading to three cases. If the splay vector on both sides of a zero-splay line points inwards towards the line, then this indicates that paths diverge as they approach the line from either side. This is an interior line of peak divergence (I-PD), and paths seeding on the line will converge when propagated away in both directions, Fig. 5B, C. Conversely, if the splay vector points away from the zero-splay line on both sides, then paths converge when approaching the line from either side. We call this an interior line of peak convergence (I-PC), and seeds launched from here will diverge when propagated away in both directions. Finally, if the splay vector points towards the line on one side, and away from the line on the other (i.e. it does not flip direction at the zero), then we have an interior line of inflection (I-I) with lines diverging as you approach from one side, and converging from the other. Only PD lines are suitable for seeding, whether they lie within the pattern or at the boundary. The classification of all types

Fig. 6. Irregular, splay containing director pattern filled splay seeding. A (i) Director pattern and (ii) the corresponding splay field with marked PD lines. B Pattern filled using splay-line seeding, which provides very uniform fill density. Positions of used seeds are marked with black dots and the slicing used the full algorithm, with aspects that are introduced later in the text, but keeping seed spacing fixed.

of boundaries and zero-splay lines is shown in Fig. 5C and also in the pattern in Fig. 5D.

Using this approach, we may identify all the PD lines in the pattern, which are then separated into equidistant seeds using the distance function from Eq. (1). Paths seeded in this manner generically give full coverage of the pattern, as they only ever converge on propagation. A preview example of the success of the splay-informed approach is provided in Fig. 6, which shows a complex director field, the corresponding splay field, the PD seed lines, and an example of a resulting slice pattern. The slice pattern is computed with the full algorithm, including path termination, and one may readily observe that some paths are terminated as they propagated away from the seed lines, in order to preserve constant density, but no additional lines/seeds need to be introduced as the splay-informed seed lines provide full coverage, and lines always converge when they propagate away from them.

Although the splay-free regions generically form lines, as seen in the previous example, it is also possible for extended areas of a pattern to be splay-free: for example, an azimuthal pattern or a monodomain has no splay anywhere. Furthermore, such splay-free regions can be categorised into two types requiring different seeding approaches. In the first type, segments of integral curve with zero splay traverse the region, entering and exiting at either a pattern boundary or at a splay-containing region (e.g. uniaxial monodomain). In this case, any point along the splay-free segment is an equivalent choice for seeding, and we take the mid-point of the segment for inclusion in the seed line. For a continuous sequence of splay-free segments (i.e. within a splay-free area), these mid-points join to form a continuous seed line, (seen in Fig. 4B) that traverses the splay-free area. In the second case, the director curves in the splay-free area close into a loop (e.g. azimuthal director on disk domain) and thus there is no sense of a mid-point. In this case, it is not obvious how to take a point on each director loop to form a suitable seed line. However, since such regions are entirely self-contained splay-free regions which, and splay is the main source of difficulty in seeding, they are actually very simple to seed appropriately. For example, such regions are always perfectly seeded by (straight) dual lines. We thus initially discard such regions during splay-based seeding, and return to them in a subsequent dual-line reseed step (see below).

In principle splay-informed filling directly provides complete coverage of the pattern, so, after finding all such seed lines, one should not need to generate more. However, in practice, it is possible for fillable gaps to remain after exhausting the splay-informed seed lines, both in the splay-free loop regions discussed above, and due to practical issues relating to termination (next section). After finishing with the splay-informed seed lines, it is thus sensible to consider whether there are remaining fillable areas, and, if so, to create new seed lines in them, until filling is complete. This step is already anticipated in our high-level flowchart (Fig. 3B), where the set of splay-informed seed lines form the initial seed line set anticipated in the first box, while, after these are exhausted, a box to the side anticipates new seed lines being created if fillable areas remain. For this “re-seeding” step, we revert to

Fig. 7. Seeding and spacing algorithms. Splay seeding is used for initial line seeding, while dual seeding is used for reseed. Line spacing is identical for all types of seed lines.

a standard dual line approach [72] which will provide perfect coverage for any splay-free loop regions. More precisely, we select a point in the unfilled area, propagate a dual line from the point in both directions, until it goes out of bounds or hits a filled area, then use this line as the next seed line. The choice of starting point for the dual line is made randomly, but weighted towards low splay areas, to ensure that any splay-free loop areas are taken first, and as was also previously observed to be optimal for the radial patterns. Such new seed lines are created, divided and propagated until no fillable areas remain.

In Fig. 7, we provide more flow charts summarising the creation of splay-informed seed lines and dual-line seed lines. The splay-informed diagram provides additional detail for the first box on the high level diagram (initial seed lines), while the dual-line diagram fleshes out the later re-seeding (new seed line) box.

2.3. Line propagation and termination

Having ensured that all paths are seeded, we turn our attention to how to propagate and terminate lines to best avoid overlaps and gaps. Basic numerical propagation is very simple: from a current (i th) end point of a path $\mathbf{r}_i = (x_i, y_i)$, at which the director is \mathbf{n}_i , we propagate a small straight step of length d/l along $\hat{\mathbf{n}}$, to get $\mathbf{r}_{i+1} = \mathbf{r}_i + \hat{\mathbf{n}}_i d/l$. Repeating this forms a print path, as a union of short straight segments. This approximation is satisfactory to the true integral curve, provided d/l is small compared to the radius of curvature. In practice, we allow the user to set d/l based on the pattern, although *Vector Slicer* does include an option for dynamic adjustment of d/l to resolve sharp features such as kinks.

While propagating a line, we need to terminate it if it starts to overlap with an already filled region. Taking as an example the radial pattern, paths originate from the boundary but all converge to a single point in the centre, Fig. 8A. The simplest way of termination is to do so based on the distance d from a centre-line of a currently propagated path to areas filled by previously propagated paths, and terminating the path when $d \leq d_t$, where d_t is the termination distance, and d

Fig. 8. Path termination. Propagation of lines in section of a radial pattern A without termination criterion, B with termination based on distance between centre line and previously filled pattern with thresholds (i) $d_t = 0$ and (ii) $d_t = w/2$. C Patterns filled with varied termination distances for seed separation of $d_s = w$ and D with seed spacing adjusted based on the termination distance. Arrows mark the order of seed propagation, which remains unchanged for all patterns in A and B, and likewise in C and D. The generation of slices in C and D did not use reseeded to highlight the consequences of termination.

is the distance from the centre-line of currently propagated path to the nearest filled region. When $d_t = 0$, paths are terminated only when their centre-line enters a filled area, which minimises holes at the cost of significant overlap, Fig. 8B (i). Conversely, for $d_t = w/2$ paths terminate before any overlap occurs, which eliminates overlaps at the cost of significant gaps, Fig. 8B (ii). By exploring values between these extremes, one can trade off between these two competing priorities (Fig. 8C), with the termination distance likely being both pattern and application dependent, as some applications may penalise more than overlaps or vice versa.

However, having too big of a termination radius will interfere with the seeding, as seeds are spaced at a distance of w , so if the termination distance is $d_t = w/2$, only every second seed will be utilised, Fig. 8C (iii). As anticipated previously, it can thus be advantageous to space the seeds with an effective width $d_s > w$, as seen in Fig. 8D.

Patterns filled using the termination, still exhibit undesired features. Firstly, one can identify termination fronts, along which alternate lines are terminated, leading to a radius-dependent jump in fill density by 50% (Fig. 9A), with the low density side of the jump exactly being a web-like print of the type we wish to avoid. Secondly, neighbouring paths occasionally terminate almost simultaneously, creating larger gaps that could still accommodate a path (Fig. 9B). In order to avoid these issues, we slightly relax the constraint that paths need to exactly follow the director. We do so by introducing a repulsive “force” that steers the currently propagating path away from the filled area, until it is close to perfectly abutting. We note that due to the use of paths of finite width, there always will be some disagreement between printed director and the target director, therefore the repulsion does not introduce a new class of imperfections, but rather allows us to trade of the degree of disagreement against other priorities.

Since the priority with repulsion is to encourage good packing with constant width w (rather than to maximise spacing) we need a short-ranged approach that only acts on actual overlaps. To do this, during each propagation step in which the path would extend by $\hat{n}dl$ we consider a line of length w perpendicular to the propagation direction and centred at the proposed end position of the print path, representing the physical extent of the path. The line may be then divided into empty/fillable and full/unfillable segments, from which we form the

vector \mathbf{c}_m that points along this line, from the proposed endpoint to the centre of mass of the fillable segment, Fig. 9C (i). If the path is propagated in a completely empty region, this vector is zero, while in vicinity of a single neighbouring path it points away from the path, Fig. 9C, and in case of neighbours on either side, it points to the midpoint between them, Fig. 9D. We then move the proposed endpoint a small amount in the direction of \mathbf{c}_m to reduce the overlap

$$\hat{n}dl \rightarrow \hat{n}dl + \alpha \mathbf{c}_m. \quad (2)$$

For each step, we progressively increase α until we reach a configuration where \mathbf{c}_m for the new endpoint is $\mathbf{0}$. For repulsion from a single neighbour, this always requires $\alpha = 2$ and eliminates the overlap entirely, whereas for a proposed path between two neighbours, the value required is $1 \leq \alpha \leq 2$, which causes the path to bisect the neighbours.

In order to allow trade-offs between overlap, holes and directionality, we introduce an upper limit α_r which corresponds to a limit on director deviation of $\arctan(\alpha_r w/2dl)$. Setting $\alpha_r = 0$ eliminates the repulsion, while raising it to $\alpha_r = 2$ maximises its effect.

In Fig. 9E we see that repulsion allows one to fill a radial pattern with minimal gaps. One caveat is that using a sequential filling causes a slip-stick character in the director, with adjacent paths packing perfectly to form regions of uniform director, and “grain-boundaries” appearing between such regions. However, by selecting seeds for propagation in random order, we drastically reduce this effect, obtaining the very satisfactory print path shown in Fig. 9E (ii). To quantify the effect of repulsion, we compare this print path to the one in Fig. 8D (ii), in which we balanced seed spacing and termination radius to obtain uniform fill, which resulted in a pattern with 95.1% coverage, 11.4% overlap and 3.04° average director error, whereas the repulsion allows improving the coverage to 96.1% and overlap to 8.12% while increasing the director error to only 4.24°.

A summary of the propagation and termination algorithm is given as a flow-chart in Fig. 10, which provides the detail for the equivalent box in the high-level diagram. Substituting all these sub-diagrams into the high-level one in Fig. 3B gives a large but complete filling flowchart, which is given in the Appendix A as Fig. 19.

2.4. Boundary of the print

At all stages, of filling, the algorithm considers areas outside of S (the target geometry) in exactly the same way it considers already filled areas. In particular, this means that seeds are never generated in these areas, and tool-paths will terminate upon collision with the boundary, just as they would on collision with another path. Consequently, the boundary is typically actually formed from a collection of path ends (as particularly evident in Fig. 8), meaning the realised boundary is to some extent pixelated at a resolution proportional to path width (similar to a “staircase effect” commonly seen between layers in AM, although here occurring within a given layer). In other contexts, one may create a final path running around the boundary to reproduce it more exactly. However, given there is not generically a director curve running around the boundary, such a path would typically have the wrong alignment, so we do not include such paths in the algorithm developed here.

2.5. Pattern quantification and optimisation

For a general pattern, an ideal slicing, where each point within the pattern belongs only to a single path with no holes and perfect agreement with the prescribed director, does not exist. Furthermore, different manufacturing methods may penalise these effects differently. For example, holes are highly undesired when printing continuous LCE films as their mechanics stem from the mechanics of sheets and the introduction of holes highly impacts their behaviour. Additionally, it is also desirable to slice the pattern using fewer longer paths in order to minimise seams and non-printing moves. The algorithm contains three

Fig. 9. Termination induced defects and repulsion. A The termination introduces very regular termination fronts, which for a radial pattern causes the pattern to have radius dependent seesaw-like path density, instead of the desired uniform density. B In some cases, the paths can be terminated off an already terminated path, which then leaves a gap within the pattern that could sustain a path. C Repulsion from a pre-existing path allows us a better packing of print-lines at a cost of directionality deviation. In detail, (i) given a proposed step, that exactly follows the director, we construct the line (length w) centred at the proposed endpoint, that represents the end of the path. If this line enters a previously filled area, the proposed new path overlaps a pre-existing one. We then identify the fillable segment of the end line and compute the displacement vector c_m from the proposed end to the centre of the fillable segment. (ii) Repulsion is then implemented by moving the proposed endpoint along c_m , until a configuration where $c_m = 0$ is reached. For repulsion from a single neighbour, this procedure eliminates overlap, C (ii), while for a proposed line between two pre-existing paths, this procedure ensures that the proposed path bisects its two neighbours D. E Examples of radial patterns filled using repulsion to increase fill uniformity. (i) Sequential seed propagation leads to undesirable “bunching”, which can be avoided by propagating the seeds in a random order (ii).

Fig. 10. Logic for propagation of paths from a collection of seeds $\{s_i\}$. The $\pm n$, corresponds to taking the step with the orientation agreeing with the direction of the previous propagation step.

parameters that influence these non-idealities: seed spacing, termination distance and repulsion strength. Furthermore, fill quality is also influenced by the choice of random ordering of the seeds and seed lines during propagation. Consequently, once a pattern is fully generated, it is sensible to assess its quality and optimise over the three generating parameters and the seed ordering.

As different AM techniques may have different priorities, there are many possible forms of the penalty function. For printing of LCEs, we found the following penalty formula to give us reliable results

$$\epsilon = n_p^{0.2} (w_h \rho_h^2 + w_o \rho_o^2 + w_d \rho_d^2), \quad (3)$$

with n_p being the path count, ρ_h the hole density (area fraction), ρ_o the overlap density and ρ_d the average difference between the slicing direction and printing direction calculated as

$$\rho_d = 1 - \langle |\hat{\mathbf{n}} \cdot \hat{\mathbf{n}}_p| \rangle, \quad (4)$$

and w_x are the corresponding weights, which are chosen to encode the desired trade-off between holes, overlaps and director fidelity.

Ultimately, this penalty function is essentially heuristic: we identified it via a process of trial and error, and found it gave consistently good results. However, we can rationalise its structure as follows. The three summed terms are dimensionless “density” objects, that are zero for a perfect print, and $\mathcal{O}(1)$ for a very unsatisfactory one. It is thus sensible to sum these objects, with weights providing a facile way of adjusting the trade-off between priorities. The square-power on the densities provides convexity in the three parameters, encouraging balanced optima to emerge. In contrast, the path-count factor enters multiplicatively, because it has a completely different scale (practically, often 10^3), that varies with the area of the print. It also cannot be straightforwardly normalised to make a density, as some patterns (e.g. a rectilinear monodomain) have a path count linear in dimension, while others (e.g. tiled patterns [46,74]) have a path count linear in area, and, in some special cases, a well-chosen space-filling curve may fill an entire print with a single path. This difference in scale motivates the multiplicative structure: if it were added to the sum, it would likely either dominate or be irrelevant. In this structure, the power of n_p acts similar to a weight. However, we find that the power of 0.2 is consistently a good choice, that strongly motivates very low path-count configurations when they are available, but is relatively agnostic about the exact number of paths when the count needs to be high. In contrast, appropriate values of the w_x weights for LCE printing are obtained by searching the parameter space, as discussed in the results (Section 3.3).

While we decided to work with this form of a penalty function, it can be easily adjusted to other manufacturing processes, either by modification of weights or its functional form. For example, if controlling the amount of extruded material within a slice would be of great importance, overextrusion density can be defined as $\rho_o - \rho_h$, which when paired with a large weight will become an optimisation constraint. Similarly, one could introduce weights penalising short paths, targeting a preferred average path length, or even penalising path curvature.

2.6. Generating parameter optimisation

The complete slicing algorithm takes numerous inputs. First, are the geometry, director field (and, optionally, the splay field), which define the problem to be sliced. These can be directly preprocessed to identify the splay seed lines. The filling part of the algorithm then requires four additional generating parameters (GPs), seed spacing (d_s), termination distance (d_t) and repulsion magnitude (α_r), and a numerical seed for the random number generator (i_s). In principle, we would like to optimise

Fig. 11. Optimisation wrapper for the slicer. The Bayesian optimiser first seeks the optimal set of GPs based on the median disagreement for a number of seeds, and then the optimal GPs are reevaluated for a larger number of seeds from which we select the best one(s) as the optimal tool path(s).

over these four GPs to minimise the penalty function, and hence find the best available slicing of the problem (Fig. 11).

Directly optimising over all four GPs simultaneously is challenging, as the output is fundamentally chaotic/non-smooth in the numerical seed, whereas it changes somewhat predictably with the other three. We thus conduct the optimisation in two steps, firstly optimising over (d_s , d_t and α_r) to find a trio of values that give consistently good results, then computing the fill with these values for many numerical seeds i_s , and selecting the overall best as the output.

The optimisation over (d_s , d_t and α_r) is conducted using a black-box optimiser (BayesOpt package [75]). During this optimisation, for each sample of (d_s , d_t , α_r) considered, we fill the pattern several times with different numerical seeds ($s_{opt} = \{i_s\}$, which is fixed, and in practice, contains ~ 10 seeds), and the optimisation targets the median of the resulting penalty function. Having thus found the optimal values for (d_s , d_t , α_r), these are then used with a much larger set of numerical seeds ($s_{fin} = \{i_s\}$, which contains ~ 200 seeds), to generate many candidate tool-paths, and the algorithm outputs the handful (10) of these with minimal penalty function for consideration by the user. The rationale for outputting a handful of slices is that these can be stacked as layers during printing, to avoid stacking of the imperfections (overlaps, holes, director mismatch) within a given layer, making the final print yet more mechanically uniform. One may worry that the resultant layers will have slightly different orientations, leading to interfacial failure upon actuation, and/or the generation of preferred curvature via thickness gradients in actuation as familiar from a bi-metal strip. In practice, these problems have not been observed during LCE printing, likely due to the hyper-elastic nature of the material, and the very small magnitude of the director mismatches. If such behaviour were to arise, it can naturally be mitigated by increasing the penalty for director deviations, so that the optimiser prioritises director fidelity, minimising director mismatch between layers.

2.7. Filling sequence

Although the paths are created in a random order during slicing, this does not mean they should be physically printed in the same order. In fact, in order to reduce the print time, it makes sense to minimise the total distance of non-printing moves required between paths. In the

case of vector filling, where each of the paths has a distinct beginning and an end, this problem can be reduced to the asymmetric travelling salesman problem (ATSP). However, in the case of the non-polar filling, each end of the path can be either the beginning or the end, which to the best of our knowledge is not one of the standard variations of the TSP. In order to obtain a reasonable solution we thus order the paths for printing using a nearest neighbour approach, such that the print head moves from the end of one path to the nearest available end of another path; although this is likely not optimal, we found it produced satisfactory quick experimental results.

2.8. Grid based approach — implementation details

During the description of the algorithm, all concepts were introduced in a continuous sense. Due to our motivating example of LCEs, where all known director patterns are planar, we decided to implement the algorithm on a fine grid (path width greater than pixel size). The choice to use a pixelated grid rather than a continuous/vectorial implementation is essentially pragmatic: on a grid, it is very straightforward to keep track of fillable/unfillable areas and judge proximity between paths in an entirely local way, leading directly to an implementation with a compute time proportional to filled area. Of course, one could instead create a continuous implementation, and, with sufficient care, one could still achieve linearity of compute time. However, there should be minimal difference in results provided the pixel grid is fine compared to path width.

The algorithm begins by reading in the shape array S_m together with the director array θ_m . Optionally, the user can also provide the splay array s_m , which, when the director pattern is analytically defined, is the preferred approach. If the splay is not provided, the first step is to calculate the splay-informed seed lines, the procedure in Appendix A.2.

To find the splay-informed seed lines, the algorithm then randomly chooses a pixel in the domain, propagates a director curve (of finite width), analyses the splay along this curve looking for changes of sign, and, if one is found, uses the splay either side of the sign change to identify whether it has a PD character (Fig. 5). If a PD sign-flip is found, the associated pixels are stored. This procedure repeats for new random starting points, until every pixel in the domain has been considered at least once. The result is a set of pixels marked as PD points within the pattern (and on its boundary), which generically form a set of curved lines. To identify and extract the lines, we use a standard graphics idea, first adding to the set of PD points all neighbours within a $w/2$ radius (fattening), and then thinning using the Zhang-Suen algorithm [76] to get a set of pixel-thin PD lines. (The reason for first growing and then thinning the PD lines is to increase the quality and ensure continuity of the lines obtained from the splay analysis.) After doing so, the set is separated into seed lines according to simple pixel adjacency.

This concludes the preprocessing step, and the filling continues exactly as described in previous sections.

Due to implementation on a grid, pixel-based coordinates are the natural output and such, the algorithm does not generate a G-code file, but a pixel based list of paths. However, the paths can be easily converted to the desired G-code format by simple scripts, which, in principle, can be as simple as multiplying the resulting coordinates by physical pixel size and supplementing them with the corresponding G-commands. We provide a programme which was designed to be used with Hyrel's 30M printer, the details of which can be found in the Data availability.

3. Results

The algorithm is implemented in C++ (code provided as *Vector Slicer*). We now test and validate the algorithm, and demonstrate that it is capable of slicing even complex LCE director patterns.

The main results are organised as follows. We first quantify the runtime of the *Vector Slicer*. Second, we confirm that we have satisfactory

Fig. 12. The algorithm's performance on a radial pattern with path width taken to be 9 pixels, which shows linear time complexity in the considered area for both preprocessing and filling.

slicing of the simple splay-free patterns, where ideal slicing is possible. Third, we use the radial pattern as the prototypical splay-bearing pattern, and use it to explore the effect of the weights in the penalty function (w_h , w_o , w_d). We then select the best weights for our needs, and confirm that a corresponding physical printed LCE sample actuates as expected. Finally, we draw on the prior literature (LCE and AM) to consider a wide-ranging “obstacle course” of more complex patterns, and quantify *Vector Slicer*'s performance both in terms of run-time, slice-quality and actuation of physical LCE prints.

The physical printing of LCE samples closely follows the method in [26] (and described in the introduction). Precise synthetic, printing and actuation parameters are given in Section 5.

3.1. Numerical performance

For the results in this manuscript, *Vector Slicer* was run on Intel® i9-11900 (8 physical cores) with 32 GB DDR4 RAM, running Ubuntu 22.04. Pattern initialisation is single-threaded, while the many fills required for optimisation are parallelised, with each fill from a different numerical seed running completely independently on a different thread.

We start by slicing a simple radial pattern on a disk, with a path width of 9 pixels and varying total area/radius, to provide an initial benchmark for the computational speed. We typically run the algorithm using 8 threads, and the maximum recorded memory usage for a pattern with diameter of 1821 pixels, or 200 paths, was 1 GB.

Due to the implementation on a fine rectilinear grid, the run-time is linear in the number of pixels (and hence quadratic in radius) as demonstrated in Fig. 12. The preprocessing time (which mainly includes computing splay-informed seed lines) averaged 700 ns per pixel, while an individual filling takes 52 ns per pixel on a single thread. A typical LCE print has linear dimension ~ 2 cm and $w \sim 200$ μ m, requiring $\sim 10^6$ pixels, and hence a fill time of 50 ms, and a preprocessing time of 700 ms.

Running the Bayesian optimisation inevitably increases run time significantly, as firstly it requires many fills to be generated, and secondly relearning of the Bayesian model takes a significant amount of time, though this effect is amortised for larger patterns. During each iteration of the Bayesian optimisation, 32 separate fills were evaluated for each trio of GPs, and typically 200–300 trios were needed to find an optimal value, leading to $\sim 10^4$ pattern fills. The final optimisation stage was carried out with 200 numerical seeds (200 more fills) and the 10 best resulting slices were exported for slicing. Overall, this level of optimisation thus increased typical total run time to 10 s–100 s of seconds.

Fig. 13. Splay-free patterns for initial validation. Each pair of images corresponds to (left) the design showing director in blue with the I-PD seeding lines marked with black dashed lines (generated with Matplotlib's streamplot routine [77]), and (right) the sliced pattern with black dots marking positions of used seeds. Uniaxial monodomain pattern on a rectangular domain with director A along the long side, B along the short side, C at 45° and D on a complex domain, where the uniform colour density indicates perfect filling without gaps or overlaps. Azimuthal director pattern on E square and F disk domains. (For interpretation of the references to colour in this figure legend, the reader is referred to the web version of this article.)

We note that, if the algorithm were to be used in the context of variable width printing, optimisation would be redundant as slicing the pattern using seed spacing equal to path width, without repulsion, and termination radius of zero would lead to paths with widths ranging from $1/2 w$ to w . In that scenario, the execution time will be in order of single seconds.

3.2. Splay-free patterns

We next confirm that the standard splay-free director patterns commonly used for printing of LCEs can be reliably sliced. In these simple cases, there exists an ideal slicing solution (zero penalty function), so optimisation should produce good results irrespective of the relative weights used.

Firstly, we test the uniaxial monodomain pattern on rectangular domain with different orientations of the director (Fig. 13A–C), which in all three tested cases resulted in perfect coverage. As the uniaxial patterns are splay-free and every integral curve terminates at a boundary, the algorithm uses a mid-point approach for selection of seed lines, which for rectilinear domain results in a single continuous line. However, when the domain is more complicated as for example the one in Fig. 13D, the algorithm finds multiple seed lines, but due to consistent spacing, the filling is of equally high quality as for the rectangular domain.

The other popular splay-free pattern is an azimuthal pattern, which when sliced on a square domain (Fig. 13E) contains four I-PD seed lines in all four corners of the pattern, as the director curves in these regions terminate at the boundary. In contrast, the paths in the central disk (radius equal to 0.5x side-length) form closed loops, which causes the algorithm to omit them during the initial seeding, anticipating they will be instead covered by dual line re-seeding. However, the *Vector Slicer* finds a better solution – propagated paths are repulsed both by the boundary and previously propagated paths, which when propagating in circles results in the creation of Archimedean spiral, filling the whole inner part of the pattern while utilising only a single path. We observe analogous behaviour when slicing an azimuthal pattern on a disk domain (Fig. 13F) – again a single seed at the boundary generates a spiral solution for the whole disk. In this case, there are in principle no suitable PD lines to create the initial splay-informed seeds, but such an optimal seed can arise either during dual-line re-seeding or via discretisation errors in the initial splay-informed consideration of the boundary.

Fig. 14. Influence of using different penalty weights during slicing optimisation. Each of the patterns is the optimal slicing for the corresponding disagreement function, and the image corresponds to the plot of the density within the pattern. Quantified pattern quality is displayed below each pattern. All patterns were sliced using $w_d = 40$, while $w_h \in \{0.05, 5, 500\}$ and $w_o \in \{0.01, 1, 100\}$ were constant within rows and columns, respectively.

3.3. Identification of suitable penalty function weights

In patterns that do contain splay, such perfect slicings do not exist, and one must trade off gaps against overlaps and orientational fidelity. In such cases, the obtained optimal pattern depends on the form of the penalty function, and we first seek to establish a suitable penalty function for printing of LCEs. For benchmarking, we use a highly splayed radial pattern in which all paths converge to a single point in the centre.

Fig. 14 shows how altering penalty weights for holes and overlaps affects the optimised configuration. Intuitively, higher overlap penalty (moving right) leads to fewer overlaps and more holes, while higher gap penalty (moving down) leads to more overlaps and fewer holes, which can be qualitatively from the slice images seen in Fig. 14, and quantitatively in the inset figures of merit (coverage, overlap and director disagreement). As the overall scale of the penalty function does not change the location of the minimum, the influence of the director penalty is shown on the diagonal with high director penalty (top left) showing more gaps and overlaps and reintroduction of termination fronts, while low director penalty (bottom right) shows more uniform path density but becomes prone to bunching.

From these nine slices presented in Fig. 14, we fabricated the numbered three, which include one example with many overlaps (#1, extreme gap avoidance), one with many gaps (#3, extreme overlap avoidance) and the compromise between them (#2). Looking at the single-layer physical prints under crossed polars (Fig. 15A) we observe the characteristic Maltese-cross pattern corresponding to an aligned radial pattern in all three samples. Furthermore, we see that #1 and #2 both form continuous sheets, while #3 contains so many elongated gaps that it forms a highly-undesirable mesh-like structure.

We then fabricated thicker, 4-layered sheets, where each layer used a distinct numerical seed as to avoid stacking the gaps/overlaps (Section 2.5). Nevertheless, the pattern #3 still had the undesirable

Fig. 15. Visual and mechanical comparison of three radial patterns with labelling corresponding to that in Fig. 14. A Micrographs of three printed patterns shown between crossed polarisers. Patterns consisted of a single $\approx 120 \mu\text{m}$ thick layer, were sliced and printed assuming print width of $w = 200 \mu\text{m}$, and have radius $r = 10 \text{ mm}$. B Photographs of 4-layered prints ($t \approx 480 \mu\text{m}$). C Simulation of the anti-cone actuation of radial patterns under thermal stimulation for progressively increased values of spontaneous strain. For higher values of spontaneous strain, the simulations resulted in self-intersecting sheets, which experimentally corresponds to contacting material. D Actuation of the samples at $140 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$ after 5 min of temperature equilibration, with the sample #2 showing actuation the closest to the simulated one.

mesh-like structure, while patterns #1 and #2 both formed continuous sheets (Fig. 15B). The extent of gaps and overlaps in the slicing was quantified by weighing the printed specimens, and comparing their areal density to a perfectly sliced linear monodomain print (0.050 g/cm^2). We observed that #1 is 17% denser (indicates overlapping print paths have resulting in increased thickness and smearing of the ink), #3 is 24% less dense (as is intuitive from the gaps in the mesh structure) while #2 is within 0.6% of the monodomain density.

However, the quality of the prints can best be seen by comparing their actuation against the designed one. By design, the radial pattern ought to form an anti-cone shape [45], shown in Fig. 15C, that becomes increasingly closed for higher values of spontaneous strain. Indeed, all three samples form satisfactory anti-cones upon heating, suggesting that the slicing approach is reassuringly robust. Of the three samples, the #2 matches the simulations the closest (Fig. 15D and Mov. 1. We note that the incomplete actuation of #1 likely stems from it being thicker, but also due to it having weaker alignment due to smudging of ink during printing of overlaps. Combining the figures of merit, visual appearance, density measurements and actuation performance, we conclude that #2 exhibits best printing parameters. We thus use these weights ($w_h = 5$, $w_o = 1$, $w_d = 40$) for slicing all the remaining patterns in this report.

3.4. Patterns known from LCE field

Having found a suitable penalty function, we now demonstrate the capacity of the slicer on a range of previously designed patterns known from LCE literature, which form an obstacle course of useful patterns of different character. The uniformity of resulting fillings will depend on the divergence within the pattern, but for all patterns considered, the coverage remained above 95% with the overlap usually remaining below 10%, and the average director error remained below 5° . A summary of all the figures of merit, and the associated run-times for all the patterns, are gathered in Table 1.

As a first example, we take a trio of axis-symmetric spiral patterns on annular domains, that are chosen to remain Gauss flat during the actuation [53]. Our first such pattern provides an iris-like mode of actuation (Fig. 16A) by morphing the initial annulus into an annulus where the outer radius remains unchanged but the inner one

Fig. 16. Axisymmetric director patterns. A iris ($r_{in} = 5$ mm, $t \approx 480$ μm), B cylinder ($r_{in} = 5$ mm, $t \approx 480$ μm) and C evertor ($r_{in} = 10$ mm, $t \approx 720$ μm) designed for 50% contraction [53]. Black circles mark the theoretical B-PD, and black dots mark utilised seeds.

increases. Our second pattern morphs an annulus into a cylindrical shell (Fig. 16B), while the third one everts the annulus such that the inner radius becomes the outer one and vice versa (Fig. 16C). The original work on designing these patterns [53] demonstrated iris and cylinder actuation in samples fabricated via photopatterning, but was unable to demonstrate the evertor. Each pattern was tailored to hit the target shape at an actuation strain of $\epsilon = 0.5$ (actuation strain of uniaxial sample in Fig. 1B), which following [53] determined the ratio between the inner and outer annulus radii. During slicing, *Vector Slicer* correctly identified B-PD lines for seeding around the outer radius of the iris and the inner for both cylinder and evertor. Upon printing, we obtain high quality films which actuate precisely as designed as shown in Fig. 16 and Mov. 2.

We next consider a set of patterns that lack axis-symmetric and encode non-zero distributions of Gauss curvature upon actuation. Firstly, we take two translationally invariant patterns encoding uniform negative and positive Gauss curvature [48] inscribed on circular domain (Fig. 17A and B). The *Vector Slicer* correctly detects the B-PD section of perimeter in the negatively Gauss curved pattern and the I-PD line down the symmetry axis of the positive one. On actuation (Fig. 17 and Mov. 3), the pattern with constant negative Gauss curvature forms a saddle shape on heating while the positive one forms a tear drop-like section of a sphere, both closely matching the expectations [48] and the numerical simulations obtained using Morphoshell [50]. A further example of the positively Gauss curved pattern on a more complex domain can be seen in Fig. A.21.

An even lower symmetry set of patterns is provided by constant speed LC defects of different topological charges (director angle $\theta = m\phi$, where ϕ is the polar angle and m the half integer topological charge) which have been previously fabricated using photopatterning [78] and considered both theoretically and numerically [50]. We consider patterns with $m = \{3/2, -1, -2\}$ which produce complex patterns of both positive and negative Gauss curvature that varies both azimuthally and radially. As seen in Fig. 16 these patterns require seeding with a

correspondingly complex combination of both I-PD and B-PD segments, but once again the algorithm detects it robustly and the printed samples actuate in good agreement with the simulations (Fig. 16 and Mov. 4.)

3.5. Examples of other patterns

Lastly, we test the slicer with two more patterns from outside the LCEs design-space, Fig. 18. The first one is a rectangular shape with circular hole within, with the director following the direction of the largest principal curvature in an infinite plate with a hole under tension — the Kirsch's solution [79]. Due to the similarity with the problem presented in [61], we chose to match the object's dimensions and used path width of $w = 0.5$ mm instead of our standard 0.2 mm. Our algorithm obtained coverage of 98.1% while keeping the overlap to 6.22% and average directionality error to 0.13° (Table 1). This may be semi-quantitatively compared to the streamline-based approach documented in [61], which produces a coverage of 87% (overlap unknown but present).

The same design but with a smaller hole diameter of 6 mm and a narrower path spacing $w = 0.4$ mm was also sliced in [70] using the swarm [70] and global optimisation (stripe-pattern) approaches [35]. In this geometry, our algorithm¹ resulted in coverage of 97.3%, overlap of 2.52% and average directionality error 0.05° . In [70], slice quality is characterised by a path width standard deviation, σ , that loosely corresponds to a gaps/overlaps percentage, and an average director disagreement $\beta = \langle |\hat{\mathbf{n}} \cdot \hat{\mathbf{n}}_p| \rangle$, which may be compared to our $1 - \rho_d = 0.99995$ (though [70] uses a slightly differently weighted average). The swarm approach allows one to trade off between uniformity of path width and alignment fidelity, leading to slices ranging from $\sigma = 7.8\%$, $\beta = 0.981$ (most uniform) to $\sigma = 12.8\%$, $\beta = 0.998$ (best aligned). In contrast,

¹ The disagreement function here used $w_h = 1$, $w_o = 1$, $w_d = 10^{-5}$ to give a symmetric penalty to holes and overlaps.

Fig. 17. Complex director patterns. Patterns ($r = 10$ mm, $t \approx 480$ μm) with constant A negative and B positive Gauss curvature [48], and topological defects with charges C $3/2$, D -1 and E -2 [50,78]. Simulations were generated with *Morphoshell* [50]. Solid black lines are B-PD lines, and the dashed black lines are I-PD seeding lines and black spots mark seeds that were used in tool-path creation.

the global optimisation always targets uniform width, and obtained $\sigma = 2\%$, and $\beta = 0.983$. Overall, this suggests our approach achieves highly competitive uniformity of coverage, along with substantially better alignment. The latter may seem insignificant, given all β are close to one, but this is a bit misleading, since the pattern is very close to uniformly aligned, the averages over the whole sample disguise the true level of angular disagreement in the small non-uniform region around the hole.

The second pattern did not come from any previous design space, but was selected to be irregular both in the geometry (multiple holes, disconnected regions, complex shapes) and in the director structure (rapid variations throughout, including defects). As seen in Fig. 18 B, *Vector Slicer* identified the PD lines and created a good filling nevertheless, reproducing both the complex director and the complex geometry.

4. Discussion

This paper has sought to solve the problem of 3D printing of LCE sheets with arbitrary planar geometry and arbitrary planar director

pattern. In order to achieve this, we have developed a new slicing approach that builds the LCE sheet from equal-width print paths that trace along the desired director. The key difficulty is that regions of convergence/divergence in the director pattern cause convergence/divergence in the paths, requiring paths to be seeded and terminated carefully to maintain an even density. No perfect solution exists to this slicing problem. However, we find that an approach that uses splay-based path seeding and case-by-case optimisation nevertheless delivers slicing paths that are consistently good enough to enable high quality LCE prints, performance of which quantitatively matches numerical results [52]. The original problem is thus solved, enabling 3D printing of LCEs to create sophisticated patterned sheets previously only achievable via photopatterning.

Although previous works have considered similar slicing problems in other contexts [33–35,61,65,69,70], our algorithm differs in the use of seed lines (common in flow visualisation, but not AM) the development of splay-informed seed line generation (we believe previously unreported), the development of path “repulsion” to encourage neighbouring paths to exactly abut, and the use of optimisation to trade off gaps, overlaps and director fidelity. Our approach can handle

Fig. 18. Patterns with weaker symmetries. A (i) Field lines of principal stress in Kirsch's solution on rectangular geometry of 150×36 mm with a centred hole with diameter of 9 mm and (ii) the tool paths obtained from the *Vector Slicer* for path width of 0.5 mm. B Irregular pattern demonstrating *Vector Slicer*'s robustness when used on complex fields and non-trivial geometries.

the very strongly varying director patterns commonly encountered in the LCE literature, and also avoids mesh-type prints, with long paths running parallel but not physically connected, which are commonly observed in previous slicing approaches, but highly undesirable for LCEs.

We hope that this tool will be of use to many in the LCE 3D-printing community. Consequently, this manuscript is accompanied by a release of *VectorSlicer*, an open source implementation of the slicing approach, and also by a simple script for translating the resulting sliced patterns into G-code suitable for the ubiquitous 30M printer from Hyrel3D. *VectorSlicer* is also provided with a library of patterns and slices covering many of the patterns previously designed and demonstrated in the LCE literature. We note that the run-time of *VectorSlicer* is typically 10–100 s for centimetre scale LCE prints, while the physical print time is typically around an hour, so, although slicing is not very fast, it is not the rate limiting step. Furthermore, given the various generating parameters in the algorithm (line spacing, termination radius, repulsion) affect the slicing in a somewhat predictable way, it is likely that the current black-box optimisation over these parameters could be satisfactorily replaced, for examples by developing heuristics for selecting parameters, or even training a surrogate ML model. Given the current run-time is dominated by the optimisation, such an approach could potentially bring run times down to ~ 1 s, which suffices to initialise and compare tens of fills.

We also note that *VectorSlicer* is already suitable for AM of a range of other extrusion processes, where the extrusion direction aligns a material property. In particular, we hope it will be useful for the AM of ultra-strong kevlar-type LC fibres [27] and fibre-reinforced composites [12], and in bio-printing contexts where spatial control over cell orientation is desired. Furthermore, in contexts where having segments of the part with directionality differing from the prescribed is not detrimental to the functionality, our slicing algorithm can be used as an infill generator, where the perimeter is obtained using conventional slicer [61], which combines great geometry replication at the outside with patterned anisotropy within the part.

Looking ahead, there are several ways that our approach could be extended and improved. Firstly, in principle, it is possible to extrude LCE lines with spatially varying width, for example by varying the extrusion rate or the print-head's velocity. If the path width can be dynamically varied by 50%, this technique could allow a true perfect solution to the slicing problem. We reserve a practical implementation of this idea for further work, but note that *VectorSlicer* does already include the ideal width of each path required for such perfect packing.

Secondly, by varying these parameters, print temperature, and/or nozzle height, one can also modulate the strength of the LCE alignment from place to place in the print [80]. When coupled with *VectorSlicer*, this approach enables the fabrication of LCE sheets with control over both the direction and degree of contraction available at each point, taking 3D printing of LCEs beyond what can be achieved with surface alignment, and significantly widening the design space for LCE machines.

Thirdly, we can extend our approach for printing shells, or even bulk 3D LCEs with patterned director. Trivially, *VectorSlicer* can already slice layered structures, where each layer has its own planar geometry and director. In order to improve the computation time, the full Bayesian optimisation can be repeated only when the vector field within the slice has sufficiently changed that the previously identified generating parameters are no longer producing good results, allowing subsequent layers to be sliced 50 times faster. Printing of shells with in-plane directors is also a very natural extension, for which the splay-seeding approach will also hold. However, transition into 3D space requires switching from a grid-based implementation to an unstructured mesh (perhaps combined with a continuous spline-based approach for print paths) which requires careful implementation to retain the linearity of the algorithm with respect to the filled area.

However, actually printing such 3D structures introduces a couple of additional practical challenges: one must support the print during fabrication, which is a particularly acute problem for LCEs as the print paths must follow the director, and hence cannot generically be chosen to provide incremental support. Fortunately, there are several promising approaches, including printing on 3D supports, printing in a supportive bath [81], or printing self-supporting structures [26]. Secondly, printing in 3D also introduces the complication of ensuring the print head does not try to pass through the previously extruded material. This poses a challenging tool-path planning problems, reminiscent of those that plague traditional subtractive manufacture, and it is likely there is no satisfactory general solution, particularly given the requirement for the paths to follow the director. A promising approach has been developed for 3D SLAM AM in [34], in which the 3D fields is divided into non-planar slices following the desired orientation (such that the desired orientation lies within each sliced plane, and hence is suitable for extrusion) and director fidelity is sacrificed during this division to ensure 3D manufacturability. A non-planar version of *Vector Slicer* could then divide each slice into an actual tool path. Alternatively, for such 3D problems, one could take a “design for manufacturability” approach, and seek to include such 3D manufacturability constraints during the design of the 3D director field for a particular morphing function.

More generally, we anticipate that the general topic of AM with voxelated control over microstructure is an exciting area, with much unexplored potential. A simple classification of such problems can be obtained from the symmetry (order parameter) of the microstructural feature being voxelated. Conceptually simplest are features such as density or composition, that are described by one or many scalar fields within the print. Naively, such scalar features are not patterned by path direction, but rather by dynamically adjusting scalar printing parameters such as temperature or extrusion rate. However, if the relevant print parameter cannot be changed quickly enough for satisfactory voxelation, then it will be helpful to consider a contour plot of the relevant quantity in the printing domain, and try to print always along

Table 1

Execution time for different patterns presented in manuscript together with corresponding errors. Dimensions are based on $w = 0.2$ mm and 9 pixels per path.

Pattern name	Resolution	Dimensions	Iters ^a	Time	$1 - \rho_h$	ρ_o	ρ_d	$\langle \theta_{err} \rangle$
Splay-seeding ^b (Fig. 6B)	453 × 453	8 × 8 mm	173	27 s	95.9%	11.2%	0.92%	5.67°
Longitudinal (Fig. 13A)	471 × 201	10 × 4 mm	159	13 s	100%	0%	0%	0°
Transverse (Fig. 13B)	471 × 201	10 × 4 mm	207	29 s	100%	0%	0%	0°
Diagonal (Fig. 13C)	471 × 201	10 × 4 mm	209	31 s	99.7%	0.23%	0.03%	0.35°
Irregular (Fig. 13D)	647 × 692	≈12 × 13 mm	320	117 s	99.8%	0.08%	0.004%	0.1°
Azimuthal-circle (Fig. 13E)	471 × 471	10 × 10 mm	320	107 s	99%	4.67%	0.36%	3.34°
Azimuthal-square (Fig. 13F)	471 × 471	10 × 10 mm	207	47 s	98.3%	6.37%	0.76%	3.93°
Iris (Fig. 16A)	965 × 965	≈17 × 17 mm	320	174 s	97.7%	6.5%	0.08%	1.19°
Cylinder (Fig. 16B)	1292 × 1292	≈23 × 23 mm	320	295 s	96.9%	8.17%	0.22%	2.26°
Evortor (Fig. 16C)	1533 × 1533	≈28 × 28 mm	280	295 s	96.6%	10.9%	0.09%	1.66°
Negative GC (Fig. 17A)	921 × 921	20 × 20 mm	320	202 s	96.6%	10.7%	0.25%	1.62°
Positive GC (Fig. 17B)	921 × 921	20 × 20 mm	193	95 s	98%	5.68%	0.29%	1.53°
Topological defect 3/2 (Fig. 17C)	921 × 921	20 × 20 mm	286	175 s	96.5%	10.4%	0.27%	2.24°
Topological defect -1 (Fig. 17D)	921 × 921	20 × 20 mm	320	198 s	98%	9.3%	0.51%	2.35°
Topological defect -2 (Fig. 17E)	921 × 921	20 × 20 mm	320	203 s	96.7%	9.1%	0.54%	3.12°
Kirsch pattern - 9 mm hole (Fig. 18A) ^c	2720 × 668	150 × 36 mm	320	433 s	98.1%	6.22%	0.008%	0.13°
Kirsch pattern - 6 mm hole ^d	3395 × 831	150 × 36 mm	290	656 s	97.3%	2.52%	0.005%	0.07°
Irregular pattern (Fig. 18B)	1293 × 1429	29 × 32 mm	214	142 s	96.6%	11.1%	0.4%	2.46°

^a Inclusive of initial iterations.^b Seed spacing was fixed as at this point in the manuscript to $d_s = w$.^c $w = 0.5$ mm to match [61].^d $w = 0.4$ mm to match [70], and the disagreement function was set to $w_h = 1$, $w_o = 1$, $w_d = 10^{-5}$.

the contours so that the feature changes as slowly as possible. This problem is already exactly that tackled by *VectorSlicer*.

The next level of sophistication are uniaxial materials, such as nematics or fibre-elastomer composites, that are described by the orientation of a single non-polar director. In such cases, it is natural for alignment to couple to the non-polar stresses caused by extrusion, leading to alignment along the print path. This is the problem *VectorSlicer* is designed to solve. Such problems can be naturally extended by also seeking control over the degree of alignment, which cannot also be handled purely by slicing, but instead requires an additional scalar print parameter to be dynamically varied. In this case, if the additional parameter is not agile enough for voxelation, one cannot deploy the contour trick as print direction is already determined, but one can perhaps achieve a big improvement by suitably dividing and ordering the print paths to require only gradual changes.

Beyond nematic-type alignment, one can consider voxelating truly vector order, as found in ferroelectrics, piezoelectrics, or polar biological tissues. This question is likely to soon be relevant for LCEs, as ferroelectric nematics have recently been reported [82], although not yet made into elastomers. Such vector order can in principle be aligned along a printing direction, which is itself a vector, leading to a highly analogous slicing problem that *VectorSlicer* is already equipped to solve. However, given the stresses generated during extrusion are non-polar, it is not likely that extrusion based printing will actually generate such vector alignment; more likely one will obtain a polydomain with regions pointing both up and down the print path irrespective of print direction. To our knowledge, successful vector printing has not been demonstrated in any context, but could perhaps be achieved by exploiting a true vector field aligned with the print path, such as a strong aligning magnet mounted on the head or the temperature gradient from hot reservoir to cold bed [13]

Finally, one can also imagine voxelating the orientation of even lower symmetry phases, such as orthombic crystals or biaxial nematics, where one must simultaneously specify two different material axes. In such cases, print path may sensibly determine one axis, but the second axis will require an additional directional control parameter, such as an E/B field.

Overall, this survey reveals a strong relationship between print-path selection and voxelation of microstructure, suggesting print-path planning will be a useful tool for AM whenever scalar, uniaxial or bi-axial patterning is required. We hope that the development of *VectorSlicer* provides a useful first step.

5. Materials and methods

5.1. LCE ink

The LCE ink was synthesised from mesogenic diacrylate RM82 (CAS 125248-71-7, purchased from Dakenchem), chain extender NBA (CAS 109-73-9, purchased from Merck) in molar ratios of 1.1:1, with an addition of 1.5 wt % of photoinitiator I-2959 (CAS 106797-53-9, purchased from Fluorochem). All reagents were used as received without additional purification.

The synthesis begins by adding together RM82 and I-2959 to a vial with magnetic mixer, and melting at 120 °C until fully dissolved. NBA is then added off the hotplate and the resulting mixture is vortex-mixed and transferred to a hotplate at 80 °C where it is mixed using a magnetic mixer for 30 min. Then, the LCE precursor is transferred to the syringe which will be later used for printing, in which it cures for a further 18 h in an oven at 80 °C.

5.2. Printing parameters

The printing was done using Hyrel's KR2-15 print head, using 0.3 mm brass MK8 nozzle. The print-head was heated to 80°reeC and given 30 min for temperature to equilibrate before the printing. Before each print we primed the flow by extruding 40 000–120 000 pulses (~35 – 90 μL, 1297 pulses/μL) of ink and after each print retracted the same amount. While the first prints with a new reservoir often had overextrusion issues, keeping the primed and retracted volumes constant and feed rate with the theoretical, resulted in stabilisation of the flow over the first few prints.

The printing was done on glass slides covered with a PVA sacrificial layer (5% PVA in water, spin coated and evaporated), for ease of detachment as cured samples detach by themselves when placed in the water for an extended period of time. Printing moves had a speed of 240 mm/min and non-printing moves 3000 mm/min without any retraction between them. The layer height was set to 120 μm, with the first layer being empirically set by first placing the nozzle too high above the print bed, so that the printed ink formed droplets instead of uniform-width paths, and then lowering it in 25 μm intervals until uniform-width paths are obtained. Then, the first layer height was taken to be 75 μm below the last height where droplet formation was observed.

Table 2

Formulas for all director patterns which are known from prior literature. Patterns which are not included in this table, did not have any designed functionalities and were created just to showcase the algorithm. ϕ is the polar angle.

Name	Formula or source
Uniaxial	$\theta = const$
Radial	$\theta = \phi$
Azimuthal	$\theta = \pi/2 + \phi$
Positive GC	$\arccos\left(\frac{y}{w}\right)$ [48]
Negative GC	$\pi/2 + \arccos\left(\frac{y}{w}\right)$ [48]
Topological defect	$\theta = c\phi$, with c being charge [50,78]
Iris, cylinder, evertor	Director and radius based on [53]
Kirsch's pattern	the largest principal stress in [79]

During the print, the 365 nm UV array from Hyrel was on at 50% duty cycle. After the print, the sample was cured in a custom-built UV oven composed of two 365 nm LEDs placed both above and below the sample at a distance of ~ 5 cm, for at least 8 h to ensure complete cross-linking, and then PVA layer was dissolved in water in order to detach the sample from the glass slide.

5.3. Actuation

All samples were actuated on a hot-plate covered by a Petri dish during the heating and then uncovered for cooling. The material reaches its full contraction at around 130 °C but in order to obtain complete and uniform contraction within the sample, which was generally non-planar, the hotplate was set to 140–150 °C and the sample was placed under a Petri dish during the heating.

5.4. Radial pattern weight measurements

The area density of uniaxial patterns of 4-layer thick of dimensions 20×10 mm was measured was 50.3 ± 0.5 mg/cm² ($n = 7$), while pattern #1 had 58.8 ± 1.2 mg/cm² ($n = 3$), #2 had 50.0 ± 0.6 mg/cm² ($n = 3$) and #3 had 38.2 ± 0.2 mg/cm² ($n = 3$).

5.5. Numerical simulations of deformations

Numerical simulations were obtained using Morphoshell, which is finite element software for deformation of sheets based on prescribed patterns of spontaneous stretch (first fundamental form) and bend (second fundamental form) [50]. The evolution is based on damped Newtonian mechanics, in the absence of any external forces, such as gravity. In our simulations, the patterns had no spontaneous bend and the spontaneous strain was gradually increased with equilibration between each step. The sheet thickness was taken to be 480 μ m for all samples. The meshes element size was set to be 1/75th of the biggest of pattern dimensions.

5.6. Mathematical formulas for director patterns presented in the manuscript

See Table 2 and Fig. 19.

CRedit authorship contribution statement

Michał Zmysłony: Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft, Visualization, Validation, Software, Methodology, Formal analysis, Data curation, Conceptualization. **Klaudia Dradrach:** Writing – review & editing, Validation, Investigation. **John S. Biggins:** Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft, Supervision, Resources, Project administration, Methodology, Funding acquisition, Formal analysis, Conceptualization.

Declaration of competing interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

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Appendix A. Derivation of used formulas

A.1. Distance function

Let us begin with two lines of constant width d that are adjacent to one another, as shown in Fig. A.20. Two points laying on the centre lines are connected with a vector \mathbf{l} , such that this vector passes through the crossing point of edges of the lines. In order to calculate the length of the vector l , we sum up

$$l = \frac{d}{2} \left(\frac{1}{\cos \alpha_1} + \frac{1}{\cos \alpha_2} \right), \quad (\text{A.1})$$

where α_i are angles between \mathbf{l} and $\hat{\mathbf{n}}_i^*$, therefore $\cos \alpha_i = \hat{\mathbf{n}}_i^* \cdot \hat{\mathbf{l}}$. The formula can be then rewritten to

$$d = \frac{2l \cos \alpha_1 \cos \alpha_2}{l \cos \alpha_1 + l \cos \alpha_2} = \frac{2|\hat{\mathbf{n}}_1^* \cdot \mathbf{l}| |\hat{\mathbf{n}}_2^* \cdot \mathbf{l}|}{|\hat{\mathbf{n}}_1^* \cdot \mathbf{l}| + |\hat{\mathbf{n}}_2^* \cdot \mathbf{l}|}, \quad (\text{A.2})$$

where d is the maximal width of adjacent lines that fits between two selected centre points.

A.2. Splay vector

Let us begin with writing the definition of \mathbf{Q}

$$\mathbf{Q} = \hat{\mathbf{n}} \otimes \hat{\mathbf{n}}. \quad (\text{A.3})$$

From the chain rule, the divergence of \mathbf{Q} is

$$\nabla \cdot \mathbf{Q} = \hat{\mathbf{n}}(\nabla \cdot \hat{\mathbf{n}}) + (\hat{\mathbf{n}} \cdot \nabla)\hat{\mathbf{n}}. \quad (\text{A.4})$$

However, by definition $|\hat{\mathbf{n}}| = 1$ and the second term is perpendicular to it at any given point, provided that $\hat{\mathbf{n}}$ is smooth. Therefore,

$$\mathbf{s} = \mathbf{Q}\nabla \cdot \mathbf{Q} = \hat{\mathbf{n}}(\nabla \cdot \hat{\mathbf{n}}) \quad (\text{A.5})$$

which retrieves the other definition of splay vector while possessing correct tensorial properties.

A.3. Numerical calculation of splay vector

As the splay vector is defined as $\mathbf{s} = \mathbf{Q}\nabla \cdot \mathbf{Q}$, and \mathbf{Q} is easily calculated from the director field, the divergence of it can be calculated from divergence theorem as

$$\nabla \cdot \mathbf{Q} = \frac{1}{2d} \left((\mathbf{Q}_{(1,0)} - \mathbf{Q}_{(-1,0)}) \hat{\mathbf{x}} + (\mathbf{Q}_{(0,1)} - \mathbf{Q}_{(0,-1)}) \hat{\mathbf{y}} \right) \quad (\text{A.6})$$

where $\hat{\mathbf{x}}$ and $\hat{\mathbf{y}}$ are corresponding versors, d is the size of the grid and subscripts denote the coordinate offset. As the algorithm is interested in where the splay vector inverts its direction, d can be set to 1. This numerical way of calculating the splay vector provides a very good approximation and is numerically stable.

Appendix B. Supplementary data

Supplementary material related to this article can be found online at <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.addma.2024.104604>.

Fig. 19. Complete filling flowchart.

Fig. A.20. Distance between the centres of two adjacent paths.

Fig. A.21. Constant positive Gauss curvature pattern on an undulated rectangular domain. A design, B slice, C print ($t \approx 480 \mu\text{m}$, $L = 40 \text{ mm}$, $w = 11\text{--}15 \text{ mm}$). D Simulation view of the same pattern at $\epsilon = 0.5$ strain from the (i) top and (ii) side and E corresponding experimental images.

Data availability

The *Vector Slicer* is available under the LGPLv3 licence at https://github.com/Zmmyslony/vector_slicer. Similarly, the *GCode Generator*, the script for translating the resulting pixel-based paths into gcode compatible with 30M printer from Hyrel3D, is available at https://github.com/Zmmyslony/Vector_Slicer_GCode under the LGPLv3 licence. The files used for printing the patterns shown in this publication can be generated using the *Vector Slicer*.

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